

cyclin dependent kinase inhibitor 2A (CDKN2A) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : CDKN2A is located at chromosome 9, band p21.3 and it codes for two proteins, including the INK4 family member p16 (or p16INK4a) and p14arf, both of which act as tumor suppressors by regulating the cell cycle. p16 inhibits cyclin dependent kinases 4 and 6 (CDK-4/6), thus activating the retinoblastoma (Rb) family of proteins, which block traversal from G1 to S-phase, while p14ARF activates the p53 tumor suppressor. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of CDKN2A, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: CDKN2A, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

*ML dicoveries of CDKN2A synergy in Meningiomas

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [4]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp

et al. [5]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angioma-tous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [6] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Wurttemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [7], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [8] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [9]. Finally, Cushing [10] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [13] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [11] and Pamir et al. [12]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. cyclin dependent kinase inhibitor 2A (CDKN2A)

The division cycle of eukaryotic cells is regulated by cyclin-dependent kinases (CDKs). Their individual sequential activation and consequent phosphorylation of critical substrates, promotes orderly progression through the cell cycle. Serrano et al. [14] reported the isolation of a human p16 complementary DNA and demonstrated that p16 bound to CDK4 and inhibited the catalytic activity of the CDK4/cyclin D enzymes. They hypothesize that p16 seems to act in a regulatory feedback circuit with CDK4, D-type cyclins and retinoblastoma protein.

Kamb et al. [15] localized a tumor suppressor locus on the short arm of human chromosome 9, to a region of less than 40 kilobases by means of homozygous deletions in melanoma cell lines. They observed that this region contained a gene, Multiple Tumor Suppressor 1 (MTS1), which encoded a previously identified inhibitor (p16) of CDK4. Further, they observed MTS1 was homozygously deleted at high frequency in cell lines derived from tumors of lung, breast, brain, bone, skin, bladder, kidney, ovary, and lymphocyte. Their findings suggested that MTS1 mutations were involved in tumor formation in a wide range of tissues.

Cytogenetic abnormalities of chromosome 9p21 are characteristic of malignant melanomas, gliomas, lung cancers and leukaemias. From a panel of 46 human malignant cell lines, via positional cloning, Nobori et al. [16] localized the most frequently deleted region on 9p21. Their sequence analysis of the isolated fragment revealed two open reading frames identical to the complementary DNA for the inhibitor of CDK4 and their PCR and Southern blot analysis confirmed the frequent deletion or rearrangement of the CDK4-inhibitor gene in melanomas, gliomas, lung cancers and leukaemias, and the absence of detectable gene transcripts. Since the CDK4 inhibitor is thought to be a physiological suppressor of proliferation, they hypothesize that cells unable to produce the inhibitor may be prone to neoplastic transformation.

The CDK inhibitor p16 is a candidate tumour-suppressor protein that maps to a genomic locus strongly associated with familial melanoma and other tumour types. Koh et al. [17] reported that p16 could act as a potent and specific inhibitor of progression through the G1 phase of the cell cycle, and demonstrated that several tumour-derived alleles of p16 encoded functionally compromised proteins. They observed that the ability of p16 to arrest cell-cycle progression generally correlated with inhibition of cyclin D1/CDK4 kinase activity in vitro. Their results provided support for the notion that p16 was an important cell-cycle regulator whose inactivation contributed to the outgrowth of human tumours.

D-type cyclins, in association with CDK-4/6, promotes progression through the G1 phase of the cell cycle by phosphorylating the retinoblastoma protein (RB). The activities of CDK-4/6 are constrained by inhibitors such as p16, the product of the CDKN2 gene on human chromosome 9p21. Further, the frequent deletion or mutation of CDKN2 in tumour cells suggests that p16 acts as a tumour suppressor. Lukas et al. [18] showed that wild-type p16 arrested normal diploid cells in late G1, whereas a tumour-associated mutant of p16 did not. Significantly, the ability of p16 to induce cell-cycle arrest was lost in cells lacking functional RB, including primary fibroblasts from Rb^{-/-} mouse embryos. Thus, loss of p16, overexpression of D-cyclins and loss of RB had similar effects on G1 progression, and may represent a common pathway to tumorigenesis.

The p16 gene (P16, MTS1, CDKN2) encodes a negative regulator of the cell cycle. Stone et al. [19] described two transcripts derived from the p16 gene with distinct protein coding potentials. They observed that the previously undescribed transcript form had the same exons 2 and 3 as the p16-encoding mRNA but contains a different exon 1.

The INK4a (MTS1, CDKN2) gene encodes an inhibitor (p16^{INK4a}) of the CDK-4/6 that blocks them from phosphorylating the retinoblastoma protein (pRB) and prevents exit from the G1 phase of the cell cycle. Deletions/mutations involving INK4a occur

frequently in cancers, implying that p16^{INK4a}, like pRB, suppresses tumor formation. Ouelle et al. [20] observe that an unrelated protein (p19^{ARF}) arose in major part from an alternative reading frame of the mouse INK4a gene, and its ectopic expression in the nucleus of rodent fibroblasts induced G1 and G2 phase arrest. They hypothesized that the unitary inheritance of p16^{INK4a} and p19^{ARF} might underlie their dual requirement in cell cycle control.

By translating the common second exon in alternative reading frames, Stott et al. [21] specified two distinct proteins encoded by the CDKN2A locus. The product of the alpha transcript, p16(INK4a), is a recognized tumour suppressor that induces a G1 cell cycle arrest by inhibiting the phosphorylation of the retinoblastoma protein by the cyclin-dependent kinases, CDK4 and CDK6. In contrast, they observed that the product of the human CDKN2A beta transcript, p14(ARF), activated a p53 response manifest in elevated levels of MDM2 and p21(CIP1) and cell cycle arrest in both G1 and G2/M. Their results place p14(ARF) in an independent pathway upstream of p53 and imply that CDKN2A encodes two proteins that are involved in tumour suppression.

The INK4a/ARF locus on human chromosome 9p resides at the nexus of two critical cell cycle regulatory pathways, the p53 pathway and the retinoblastoma (pRb) gene pathway. INK4a is a CDK inhibitor whereas ARF binds the MDM2 proto-oncogene and stabilizes p53. Robertson and Jones [22] examined the expression patterns of the INK4a/ARF locus at the RNA level in normal human and murine tissues, and found that both INK4a and ARF were expressed in most tissues at low levels detectable only by RT-PCR.

Lin et al. [23] reported the discovery of a novel variant of p16(INK4A), termed p16 γ , in a primary T-cell acute lymphoblastic leukemia (T-ALL) patient sample and a neuroblastoma cell line, which was expressed at both the transcriptional and translational levels. They cloned and sequenced p16 γ cDNA and found that p16 γ was identical to p16(INK4A), except that it contained an in-frame insertion of 197 bp between exons 2 and 3. Their structural analysis confirmed that p16 γ , like p16(INK4A), was also an ankyrin-repeat protein, while their functional analysis of p16 γ revealed that p16 γ protein interacted with cyclin D-dependent kinase 4 and inhibited its kinase activity. Using a luciferase reporter assay, they observed that the transfection of p16 γ repressed the E2F response, the downstream target of pRB, with an efficacy equivalent to that of p16(INK4A). Further, p16 γ , like p16(INK4A), induced cell-cycle arrest at G(0)/G(1), and inhibited cell growth in colony formation assay.

Boström et al. [24] investigated 20 benign meningiomas, 34 atypical meningiomas, and 13 anaplastic meningiomas, for losses of genetic information from chromosome arms 1p and 9p, as well as for deletion, mutation, and expression of the tumor suppressor genes CDKN2A (p16^{INK4a}/MTS1), p14^{ARF}, CDKN2B (p15^{INK4b}/MTS2) (all located at 9p21) and CDKN2C (1p32). Via comparative genomic hybridization and microsatellite analysis, they showed losses on 1p in 11 anaplastic meningiomas (85%), 23 atypical meningiomas (68%), and 5 benign meningiomas (25%). Taken together, their results indicated that CDKN2C was rarely altered in meningiomas, while the majority of anaplastic meningiomas either showed homozygous deletions of CDKN2A, p14^{ARF}, and CDKN2B, mutations in CDKN2A and p14^{ARF}, or lack of expression of one or more of these genes. Thus, inactivation of the G1/S-phase cell-cycle checkpoint

is an important aberration in anaplastic meningiomas.

Further, Pham et al. [25] in a systematics review, identify CDKN2-A/B as meningioma tumor suppressor genes. Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.3. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.4. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [26] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [27] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [27].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [28]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [29], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank}

Joachims [26] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM^{Rank}_{classify}$ Joachims [26]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [30], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine

ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. CDKN2A related synergies

Note - CDKN2A was found to be upregulated in Type C. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 258 2^{nd} order combinations of CDKN2A were recorded.

3.1.1. FOXM1/WNT signaling target genes in Vasudevan et al. [3]

Meningioma is the most common primary intracranial tumor, but the molecular drivers of aggressive meningioma are incompletely understood. Using 280 human meningioma samples and RNA sequencing, immunohistochemistry, whole-exome sequencing, DNA methylation arrays, and targeted gene expression profiling, Vasudevan et al. [3] defined the molecular profile of aggressive meningioma. Their transcriptomic analyses identified FOXM1 as a key transcription factor for meningioma proliferation and a marker of poor clinical outcomes, while they discovered genomic and epigenomic factors associated with FOXM1 activation in aggressive meningiomas. Finally, they defined a FOXM1/WNT signaling axis in meningioma that was associated with a mitotic gene expression program, poor clinical outcomes, and proliferation of primary meningioma cells.

Vasudevan et al. [3] provide a set of FOXM1 target genes in meningioma and they also defined a FOXM1/WNT signaling axis in meningioma that was associated with a mitotic gene expression program, poor clinical outcomes, and proliferation of primary meningioma cells. Of these, CDC28 protein kinase regulatory subunit 2 (CKS2), TPX2 microtubule nucleation factor (TPX2), DNA topoisomerase II alpha (TOP2A), cyclin B2 (CCNB2), cell division cycle associated 5 (CDCA5), trophinin associated protein (TROAP), thymidine kinase 1 (TK1), BUB1 mitotic checkpoint serine/threonine kinase B (BUB1B), centromere protein F (CENPF), kinesin family member 4A (KIF4A), NIMA related kinase 2 (NEK2), kinesin family member 18B (KIF18B), BRCA1 interacting DNA helicase 1 (BRIP1), DEP domain containing 1B (DEPDC1B) and Holliday junction recognition protein (HJURP), were found to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1].

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of CDKN2A with these genes.

Table 1 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 2 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1. The table 1 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t CDKN2A. CCNB2 - CDKN2A shows high ranking of 231 (laplace), 136 (linear), 200 (rbf), 67; BUB1B - CDKN2A shows high ranking of 142 (laplace), 147 (linear), 199 (rbf), 41.

While, CKS2 - CDKN2A shows low ranking of 119, 159, 84, 65; TPX2 - CDKN2A shows low ranking of 118, 133, 35, 206; TOP2A - CDKN2A shows low ranking of 174, 129, 119, 47; CDCA5 - CDKN2A shows low ranking of 82, 211, 48, 143; TROAP - CDKN2A shows low ranking of 135, 110, 31, 190; TK1 - CDKN2A shows low ranking of 99, 56, 228, 221; CENPF - CDKN2A shows low ranking of 84, 100, 94, 179; KIF4A - CDKN2A shows low ranking of 109, 143, 51, 141; NEK2 - CDKN2A shows low ranking of 170, 58, 53, 38; KIF18B - CDKN2A shows low ranking of 128, 135, 123, 52; BRIP1 - CDKN2A shows low ranking of 244, 150, 5, 131; DEPDC1B - CDKN2A shows low ranking of 111, 30, 57, 88; and HJURP - CDKN2A shows low ranking of 210, 131, 24, 96.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS CDKN2A				
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T CDKN2A				
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CKS2 - CDKN2A	119	159	84	65
TPX2 - CDKN2A	118	133	35	206
TOP2A - CDKN2A	174	129	119	47
CCNB2 - CDKN2A	231	136	200	67
CDCA5 - CDKN2A	82	211	48	143
TROAP - CDKN2A	135	110	31	190
TK1 - CDKN2A	99	56	228	221
BUB1B - CDKN2A	142	147	199	41
CENPF - CDKN2A	84	100	94	179
KIF4A - CDKN2A	109	143	51	141
NEK2 - CDKN2A	170	58	53	38
KIF18B - CDKN2A	128	135	123	52
BRIP1 - CDKN2A	244	150	5	131
DEPDC1B - CDKN2A	111	30	57	88
HJURP - CDKN2A	210	131	24	96

Table 1: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between CDKN2A VS Individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 graphically, with the following influ-

ences - • Individual members w.r.t CDKN2A with CDKN2A – > CDCA5 / KIF18B.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
Individual members w.r.t CDKN2A	
CDCA5	CDKN2A
KIF18B	CDKN2A

Table 2: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between CDKN2A and Individual members.

3.1.2. CDKN2A unknown combinations with high ranking

Along with the above known genes affected by CDKN2A, there are others genes that were upregulated and recorded in Patel et al. [1]. I document here, the 2nd order combinations with CDKN2A, which were assigned high rank by the machine learning based search engine. These high ranks point to the possible existence of synergy between the CDKN2A and the genetic factors, that might not have been explored till now. Further, wet lab tests will confirm the veracity of these rankings.

Of these, reticulocalbin 1 (RCN1), assembly factor for spindle microtubules (ASPM), phosphofructokinase, platelet (PFKP), Mov10 like RNA helicase 1 (MOV10L1), phosphoprotein membrane anchor with glycosphingolipid microdomains 1 (PAG1), centromere protein M (CENPM), hypoxia inducible factor 3 subunit alpha (HIF3A), CD101 molecule (CD101), nucleolar and spindle associated protein 1 (NUSAP1), kinetochore scaffold 1 (KNL1), centrosomal protein 55 (CEP55), ankyrin repeat domain 31 (ANKRD31), solute carrier family 22 member 8 (SLC22A8), SPC25 component of NDC80 kinetochore complex (SPC25), solute carrier family 16 member 12 (SLC16A12), pantothenate kinase 1 (PANK1), pleckstrin homology and RhoGEF domain containing G4B (PLEKHG4B), PDCD10 and GCKIII kinases associated 1 (PGCKA1 / C4orf19), schlafen family member 13 (SLFN13), coiled-coil domain containing 144C, pseudogene (CCDC144CP), diacylglycerol kinase iota (DGKI), H2B clustered histone 5 (HIST1H2BD), H4 clustered histone 8 (HIST1H4H), zinc finger protein 233 (ZNF233), plexin domain containing 1 (PLXDC1), coiled-coil domain containing 78 (CCDC78), tubulin epsilon and delta complex 2 (TEDC2), solute carrier family 9 member C2 (putative) (SLC9C2), melanotransferrin (MELTF), spindle and kinetochore associated complex subunit 3 (SKA3), 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratase 1 (HACD1), insulin like growth factor 2 (IGF2), chromatin licensing and DNA replication factor 1 (CDT1), cytoskeleton associated protein 2 like (CKAP2L), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily A regulatory beta subunit 3 (KCNA3), cyclin dependent kinase 1 (CDK1), ribonucleotide reductase regulatory subunit M2 (RRM2), aryl hydrocarbon receptor nuclear translocator 2 (ARNT2), C1q and TNF related 1 (C1QTNF1), exonuclease 1 (EXO1), ubiquitin conjugating enzyme E2 C (UBE2C), DnaJ heat shock protein family (Hsp40) member C22 (DNAJC22), carbonic anhydrase 8 (CA8), apolipoprotein L domain containing 1 (APOLD1), immunoglobulin superfamily member 5 (IGSF5),

IZUMO1 receptor, JUNO (IZUMO1R), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 482 (LINC00482), NDUFA4 mitochondrial complex associated like 2 (NDUFA4L2), H1.2 linker histone, cluster member (HIST1H1C), smoothelin like 2 (SMTNL2), X-ray repair cross complementing 2 (XRCC2), solute carrier family 30 member 10 (SLC30A10), protocadherin gamma subfamily A, 1 (PCDHGA1), SRRM2 antisense RNA 1 (SRRM2-AS1), mitochondrially encoded tRNA-Trp (UGA/G) (MT-TW), firre intergenic repeating RNA element (FIRRE), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 887 (LINC00887), lipocalin like 1 (LCNL1), MCM3AP antisense RNA 1 (MCM3AP-AS1), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 954 (LINC00954), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A8, pseudogene (ANKRD20A8P), DARS1 antisense RNA 1 (DARS-AS1), small regulatory polypeptide of amino acid response (SPAAR), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1564 (LINC01564), cytochrome c oxidase subunit 5B pseudogene 6 (COX5BP6), uroplakin 3B (UPK3B), RRS1 divergent transcript (RRS1-DT / RRS1-AS1), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1564 (LINC01948), high mobility group box 1 pseudogene 21 (HMGB1P21), dynein axonemal heavy chain 10 opposite strand (DNAH10OS), family with sequence similarity 218 member A (FAM218A) and DND microRNA-mediated repression inhibitor 1 (DND1), were found to be recorded as upregulated in data by Patel et al. [1]. Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2nd order combination of CDKN2A with these genes.

Table 3 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 4 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 3. The table 3 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t CDKN2A.

One can also interpret the results of the table 3 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t CDKN2A with CDKN2A – > RCN1 / ASPM / PFKP / MOV10L1 / PAG1/ CENPM / HIF3A / CD101 / NUSAP1 / KNL1 / CEP55 / ANKRD31 / SLC22A8 / SPC25 / SLC16A12 / PANK1 / PLEKHG4B / C4orf19 / SLFN13 / CCDC144CP / DGKI / HIST1H2BD / HIST1H4H / ZNF233 / PLXDC1 / CCDC78 / TEDC2 / SLC9C2 / MELTF / SKA3 / HACD1 / IGF2 / CDT1 / CKAP2L / KCNAB3 / CDK1 / RRM2 / ARNT2 / C1QTNF1 / EXO1 / UBE2C / DNAJC22 / CA8 / APOLD1 / IGSF5 / IZUMO1R / LINC00482 / NDUFA4L2 / HIST1H1C / SMTNL2 / XRCC2 / SLC30A10 / PCDHGA1 / SRRM2-AS1 / MT-TW / FIRRE / LINC00887 / LCNL1 / MCM3AP-AS1 / LINC00954 / ANKRD20A8P / DARS-AS1 / SPAAR / LINC01564 / COX5BP6 / UPK3B / RRS1-AS1 / LINC01948 / HMGB1P21 / DNAH10OS / FAM218A / DND1.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic CDKN2A 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of CDKN2A-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

RANKING UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS CDKN2A									
RANKING OF UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T CDKN2A									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
RCN1 - CDKN2A	153	162	7	165	ASPM - CDKN2A	183	139	2	203
PFKP - CDKN2A	192	254	62	219	MOV10L1 - CDKN2A	134	198	18	168
PAG1 - CDKN2A	125	188	100	204	CENPM - CDKN2A	164	190	54	231
HIF3A - CDKN2A	256	196	3	217	CD101 - CDKN2A	165	231	43	191
NUSAP1 - CDKN2A	223	173	83	170	KNL1 - CDKN2A	137	241	41	157
CEP55 - CDKN2A	226	170	99	166	ANKRD31 - CDKN2A	236	157	4	174
SLC22A8 - CDKN2A	249	257	17	220	SPC25 - CDKN2A	200	186	189	7
SLC16A12 - CDKN2A	252	256	21	249	PANK1 - CDKN2A	212	171	209	8
PLEKHG4B - CDKN2A	204	230	22	236	C4orf19 - CDKN2A	224	216	166	116
SLFN13 - CDKN2A	75	207	173	155	CCDC144CP - CDKN2A	245	227	220	54
DGKI - CDKN2A	248	132	252	28	HIST1H2BD - CDKN2A	171	199	78	152
HIST1H4H - CDKN2A	216	203	159	122	ZNF233 - CDKN2A	215	149	136	77
PLXDC1 - CDKN2A	177	90	246	233	CCDC78 - CDKN2A	189	144	185	9
TEDC2 - CDKN2A	172	140	176	119	SLC9C2 - CDKN2A	257	258	66	184
MELTF - CDKN2A	148	155	245	167	SKA3 - CDKN2A	201	213	213	145
HACD1 - CDKN2A	173	43	240	159	IGF2 - CDKN2A	218	217	65	147
CDT1 - CDKN2A	32	126	196	189	CKAP2L - CDKN2A	228	206	151	160
KCNAB3 - CDKN2A	65	202	244	176	CDK1 - CDKN2A	187	172	194	64
RRM2 - CDKN2A	144	239	183	44	ARNT2 - CDKN2A	250	252	208	127
C1QTNF1 - CDKN2A	205	255	256	2	EXO1 - CDKN2A	175	164	203	153
UBE2C - CDKN2A	219	214	247	75	DNAJC22 - CDKN2A	242	246	88	251
CA8 - CDKN2A	157	229	39	175	APOLD1 - CDKN2A	161	182	225	85
IGSF5 - CDKN2A	240	219	202	169	IZUMO1R - CDKN2A	160	181	154	218
LINC00482 - CDKN2A	241	221	214	188	NDUFA4L2 - CDKN2A	163	193	188	154
HIST1H1C - CDKN2A	258	192	114	199	SMTNL2 - CDKN2A	254	247	56	254
XRCC2 - CDKN2A	227	166	255	50	SLC30A10 - CDKN2A	179	233	80	198
PCDHGA1 - CDKN2A	186	142	232	100	SRRM2-AS1 - CDKN2A	178	228	175	56
MT-TW - CDKN2A	222	54	172	180	FIRRE - CDKN2A	230	249	111	239
LINC00887 - CDKN2A	247	232	163	161	LCNL1 - CDKN2A	253	245	128	232
MCM3AP-AS1 - CDKN2A	232	92	161	139	LINC00954 - CDKN2A	211	208	85	181
ANKRD20A8P - CDKN2A	237	234	23	258	DARS-AS1 - CDKN2A	185	220	198	78
SPAAR - CDKN2A	190	153	206	66	LINC01564 - CDKN2A	197	204	104	134
COX5BP6 - CDKN2A	243	189	192	24	UPK3B - CDKN2A	246	174	187	250
RRS1-AS1 - CDKN2A	198	116	230	178	LINC01948 - CDKN2A	151	243	229	34
HMGBlP21 - CDKN2A	229	163	142	46	DNAH10OS - CDKN2A	188	52	165	248
FAM218A - CDKN2A	176	226	241	63	DND1 - CDKN2A	126	195	235	148

Table 3: 2nd order interaction ranking between CDKN2A VS Individual members.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Unknown Individual members w.r.t CDKN2A
RCN1 / ASPM / PFKP / MOV10L1 / PAG1 / CENPM ...
HIF3A / CD101 / NUSAP1 / KNL1 / CEP55 ...
ANKRD31 / SLC22A8 / SPC25 / SLC16A12 / PANK1 ...
PLEKHG4B / C4orf19 / SLFN13 / CCDC144CP / DGKI ...
HIST1H2BD / HIST1H4H / ZNF233 / PLXDC1 / CCDC78 ...
TEDC2 / SLC9C2 / MELTF / SKA3 / HACD1 / IGF2 ...
CDT1 / CKAP2L / KCNAB3 / CDK1 / RRM2 / ARNT2 ...
C1QTNF1 / EXO1 / UBE2C / DNAJC22 / CA8 / APOLD1 ...
IGSF5 / IZUMO1R / LINC00482 / NDUFA4L2 / HIST1H1C ...
SMTNL2 / XRCC2 / SLC30A10 / PCDHGA1 / SRRM2-AS1 ...
MT-TW / FIRRE / LINC00887 / LCNL1 / MCM3AP-AS1 ...
LINC00954 / ANKRD20A8P / DARS-AS1 / SPAAR / ...
LINC01564 / COX5BP6 / UPK3B / RRS1-AS1 ...
LINC01948 / HMGB1P21 / DNAH10OS / FAM218A / DND1 CDKN2A

Table 4: 2^{nd} order combinatorial hypotheses between CDKN2A and Individual members.

Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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